

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pARTicle Data (SPEARHEAD)

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List of Acronyms

AMS	Alpha Magnet Spectrometer
BGO	Bismuth germanium oxide
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
COSTEP	Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
EPT	Electron Proton Telescope
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron
ESA	European Space Agency
FFS	Force Field Solution
FD	Forbush Decrease
FM	Failure Mode
FMO	Flight Model
G4VM	Geant4 Virtual Machine
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
GPS	General Particle Source
HED	High Energy Detector
HET	High Energy Telescope
HG	High Gain
HMI	Hahn Meitner Institut
ICME	Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection
JAXA	Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
LG	Low Gain
MC	Monte Carlo
MIP	Minimum Ionizing Particle
MOSIF	Magnetospheric Orbiter Sunshield and Interface
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
RHESSI	Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SF	Solar Flare
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer

SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SoIO	Solar Orbiter
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SQ	Science Question
SSD	Solid State Detector
TO	Technical Objective
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports on the calculation of response functions for [SOHO/Chandra - EPHIN](#), [SOHO-Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron \(ERNE\)](#), [SolO-HET](#), and [BepiColombo-SIXS](#).

The general procedure for determining the response functions of particle instruments is outlined in the introduction and more thoroughly detailed in Sections [2.1](#) - [2.2](#).

Sections [2.3](#) - [2.4](#) follow the workflow exemplary for [EPHIN](#) in great detail.

The resulting response functions for [SOHO-ERNE](#), [SolO-HET](#), and [BepiColombo-SIXS](#) are described in Sections [2.5](#) - [2.7](#).

1 Introduction

SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (**SPEARHEAD**) will provide answers to three Science Questions (**SQs**):

1. How are protons accelerated beyond 100 MeV and electrons beyond 1 MeV in solar eruptions?
2. What are the release times and spectral characteristics of near-relativistic particles from solar eruptions?
3. How do coronal and interplanetary structures affect the transport processes of very high energetic particles?

To enable the scientific data analysis **SPEARHEAD** has three Technical Objective (**TO**):

1. Determining the response functions of a large number of spacecraft instruments to derive high-energy particle fluxes from observations at unprecedented accuracy releasing revised and completely new datasets
2. Performing cross-calibration of datasets measured by science-grade and monitoring instruments to enable the use of monitoring data for scientific analyses
3. Combining high-energy particle and context observations together with modeling of plasma structures for easier in-depth analysis of solar eruptions, quantifying their effect and delivering them to the community.

Hereby **WP2** directly addresses **TO1** and supports **TO2**.

Efficiency computation for space particle instruments like **EPHIN** (Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) aboard **SOHO** of European Space Agency (**ESA**) and National Aeronautics and Space Administration (**NASA**), **EPHIN** aboard **Chandra** of **NASA**, **ERNE** (Torsti et al. 1995) aboard **SOHO**, **HET** (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020) aboard **Solo** of **ESA**, and **SIXS** (Huovelin et al. 2020) aboard **BepiColombo** of **ESA** and Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (**JAXA**) involves quantifying the instrument's ability to detect and measure particles accurately in a space environment. In more detail:

- Particle measurements consists of a set of measured quantities (like energy losses, photon detection etc.) typically quantified as count rates, energy losses in material and similar quantities C .
- At a given time t the instrument is embedded in a radiation environment consisting of different ions, electrons, and photons that are the unknown physical quantities $J_{\alpha}(E, \Omega, \mathbf{x}, t)$ to be derived. Herein E , Ω , \mathbf{x} , and α are the kinetic energy, the incoming direction, the location, and particle species, respectively.
- Both are coupled to each other as discussed by Sullivan (1971). The response functions typically depend on several factors such as the geometry, material properties, detection mechanisms, and energy thresholds of the instrument.

The workflow for computing the efficiency for a spacecraft instrument (a general simplified setup is described by Sullivan 1971, and citing authors) is summarized in Fig: 1 and given below. Section 2.1 summarizes the mathematical approach to compute the response functions utilizing the assumptions described in Sullivan (1971).

Figure 1: Workflow of computing Instrument response functions

The workflow to determine the response function of a particle instrument is displayed in Fig. 1 and can be summarized as this:

Instrument model: The **GEANT 4** instrument models are given in **GDML** file that have been discussed in **Köberle et al. (2024)** and **Köberle et al. (2025)**.

GEANT model runs: The General Particle Source (**GPS**) is used for the model computations as summarized above.

Instrument specific analysis: The output of the **GEANT** computations is utilized to compute the instrument specific data structures (see following section).

Computation of the instrument response is described above and is based on the **Sullivan (1971)** approach.

Validation: **Heber et al. (2024b)** compares the results for **EPHIN** with Alpha Magnet Spectrometer (**AMS**)-02 providing an uncertainty estimate of 20% for the model output.

2 Workflow to compute response functions

2.1 Mathematical consideration

The measured and physical quantities are interlinked by the Sullivan (Sullivan 1971) equation:

$$C(\mathbf{x}, t_0) = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T} dt \int_S \hat{\mathbf{r}} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\sigma} \int_{\Omega} d\omega \int_0^{\infty} dE \sum_{\alpha} \varepsilon_{\alpha}(E, \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \omega, t) J_{\alpha}(E, \omega, \mathbf{x}, t) \quad (1)$$

with:

J_{α} = spectral intensity of particle α

ε_{α} = detection efficiency of particle type α

t = time

t_0 = time at start of observation

T = total observation time

$d\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ = element of surface area of the last telescope sensor to be penetrated

S = total area of the last telescope sensor

$d\omega$ = element of solid angle

Ω = domain of ω ; this is limited by the other telescope sensors

\mathbf{x} = spatial coordinate of the telescope

$\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ = unit vector in direction ω

$\hat{\mathbf{r}} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ = effective element of area looking into ω

Efficiency typically depends on factors such as the geometry, material properties, detection mechanisms, and energy thresholds of the instrument. The following is a workflow for computing the efficiency for a spacecraft instrument (a general simplified setup is described by Sullivan 1971, and citing authors):

Define Instrument Geometry and Setup: As discussed in detail by Sullivan (1971) for simple instrument geometry the geometric factor can be computed analytically. The geometric factor G of a single detector of arbitrary shape with a surface A for instance is given by $G = \pi \cdot A$. Utilizing a more complex instrument, the geometrical efficiency can be computed by a Monte-Carlo method choosing randomly a starting point on one of the instrument planes and an isotropic direction (see Fig. 2). Then one computes the intersection of the track with all the material involved, i.e., other detectors that define a valid measurement for the instrument. Then the **geometrical efficiency** (ε_g) is given by:

$$\varepsilon_g = \frac{\text{Number of particles that intersect the detector}}{\text{Total number of incident particles}} \quad (2)$$

This depends on the acceptance angle, size, and shape of the detector.

Determine Detector Response: In the above case the detector is taken as ideal with a detection sensitivity of 100% for the sensitive area and 0 outside. This might not be true, and a sensitivity model

Figure 2: Sketch to illustrate the Monte Carlo approach described in Sullivan (1971).

must be taken into account (an example is given by Marquardt et al. 2015), leading to the so-called **intrinsic efficiency** ε_i that is given by

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{\text{Number of particles detected}}{\text{Number of particles incident on the sensitive area}}$$

This is influenced by the detector material and energy sensitivity.

Energy and Particle Species Sensitivity: The interaction of particles – charged or neutral – depends on the physics of energy exchange due to, e.g., Coulomb energy losses, Bremsstrahlung, hadron interaction, photon interactions, but also to scattering and particle decay and can be complex, depending on the energy range and species of particles the instrument is designed to detect. The corresponding efficiency is often expressed as a function of energy and particle type:

$$\varepsilon(E) = \varepsilon_g \cdot \varepsilon_i(E)$$

A simple example is an ideal telescope for which the energy response $R(E)$ is given by a function:

$$0 \text{ for } E < E_l \tag{3}$$

$$\varepsilon_i(E) = 1 \text{ for } E_l \leq E \leq E_u \tag{4}$$

$$0 \text{ for } E > E_u \tag{5}$$

with an energy sensitivity of 1 only within the nominal energy interval between a lower and upper energy E_l and E_u , respectively.

In order to compute efficiencies with the above-mentioned method, Monte-Carlo simulations utilizing the GEANT 4 toolkit (Agostinelli et al. 2003) are performed to model the particle interactions with the instrument and the total efficiency (this deliverable). The instrument descriptions are given in Köberle et al. (2024). In what follows, we will describe the simulation chain to derive the instrument response function. A major step in the process is the validation of the GEANT 4 model.

2.2 Realization of the MC approach utilizing GEANT's GPS

The General Particle Source (GPS) is a flexible and powerful component of the GEANT toolkit used to define and control the properties of primary particles in a simulation. It provides an extensive macro command interface that allows users to specify particle type, energy spectrum, spatial and angular distributions, and timing characteristics without modifying C++ source code and is particularly useful for:

- Emitting particles from a point, surface, or volume
- Defining directional distributions (e.g., isotropic, beam-like)
- Generating energy spectra (monoenergetic, Gaussian, histogram-based, etc.)
- Supporting time-dependent sources

GPS enables us to set up complex source configurations for detector studies, background modeling, calibration simulations, and more. It can be controlled entirely via macro files using commands as detailed below.

The computation of any response function of an Energetic Particle Instrument follows:

The implementation of a suitable particle sensor model: This has been described in Köberle et al. (2024) for SOHO EPHIN and ERNE, SoLO HET and BepiColombo SIXS. In the GPS macro, the GDML is called via:

```
/gdml/file gdml/ephin.gdml # Sets the input geometry see D2.1
/run/initialize           # Initialize the geometry
```

The description of the incident radiation: To describe the radiation environment, we use the GEANT 4 GPS (see online documentation for details). Often used is an isotropic incident of ions and electrons. As an example, the following part of a macro file is shown:

Particle type and energy

```
/gps/particle proton      # defines the particle type (proton)
/gps/ene/type Pow        # Uses a power law
/gps/ene/alpha -1.       # with spectral index -1.
/gps/ene/min 50 MeV     # with lower boundary
/gps/ene/max 6000 MeV   # and upper limit
```

Particle location and direction:

```
/gps/pos/type Surface    #Generation of particles on a surface
/gps/pos/shape Sphere    # Shape of the surface
/gps/pos/centre 0 0 -1.865 cm # Position of the sphere's center
/gps/pos/radius 30.0 cm  #center of the sphere
/gps/ang/type cos        # particle distribution approximately isotrop
```

Definition of quantities used for the analysis: In most cases, the minimum output is given by


```
/run/verbose 0 # set output level low
/event/verbose 0 # set output level low
/tracking/verbose 0 # set output level low
/sd/verbose 1 # set output to file
/sd/format evid det pvekin ioni # Quantities to write
/sd/file output/epin_protons_run # Output file
```

As examples, the full Python code is given to compute the response functions for photons in [SSD A](#), single detector counts in [SSD F](#) and for subchannels defined by energy loss masks in [EPHIN](#)'s integral channel ([Kühl et al. 2015](#)) for an isotropic [GCR](#) proton, helium, and electron flux in [appendix A5](#). For all other instruments, the computed response functions are given in the corresponding sections.

Comprehensive details on the [GPS](#) usage can be found in the official [GEANT4](#) Application Developer's Guide and the extended example codes distributed with it:

- [Geant4 Application Developer Guide](#)
- [Example: examples/extended/eventgenerator/exgps](#)

2.3 EPHIN as an example for computing response functions

Köberle et al. (2024) describes the implementation of the GEANT4 models for SOHO/Chandra - EPHIN, SOHO-ERNE, SoIO-HET and BepiColombo-SIXS utilizing GDML. It provides an overview of the GDML schema used to implement the geometry and material composition of the instruments in GEANT4. The individual models for each instrument are briefly described, highlighting the realistic implementation in comparison with the actual instruments. The models for SOHO/Chandra - EPHIN and SoIO-HET are distributed within the scope of the Geant4 Virtual Machine (G4VM) (see Gieseler et al. 2024) allowing a readily accessible simulation. A manual for setting up the G4VM is given in Appendix A of Köberle et al. (2024).

The computation of response functions is illustrated using SOHO EPHIN for:

SSD A response to photons: In Heber et al. (2025) the measurements of Solid State Detector (SSD) A is compared to measurements from the X-ray telescope aboard Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager (RHESSI). In section 2.4.1 the derivation of the response is summarized.

SSD F response to cosmic ray radiation: In Heber et al. (2024b) the measurements of Solid State Detector (SSD) F are compared to measurements from AMS-02. The corresponding derivation of the response function is described in section 2.4.2.

EPHIN's response to penetrating particles: In Heber et al. (2024b) the measurements of differential channels derived from the integral channel are compared to differential fluxes obtained by AMS-02 and is described in section 2.4.3.

2.4 Examples utilizing EPHIN aboard SOHO

EPHIN is a particle detector on board the SOHO spacecraft, launched in 1995 as a joint mission by ESA and NASA to study the Sun and the heliosphere.

EPHIN is designed to measure energetic charged particles, particularly electrons, protons, and helium nuclei, originating from the Sun and interplanetary space in the following energy ranges:

- **Electrons:** 250 keV to 10 MeV
- **Protons:** 4 MeV to 53 MeV
- **Helium nuclei:** 8 MeV/nucleon to 53 MeV/nucleon

It is based on a stack of silicon solid-state detectors arranged as a telescope, equipped with an anticoincidence system to suppress background signals that allows addressing the following science topics:

- Monitor and characterize solar energetic particle events
- Study particle acceleration mechanisms near the Sun
- Analyze particle transport processes in interplanetary space
- Provide background radiation data for other SOHO instruments

Details used in the following modeling are summarized in the appendix A3.

2.4.1 Solid State Detector (SSD) A response function to photons

The computation was performed using the geometry of the instrument described in Köberle et al. (2024) with the macro file given in Appendix A5:

A rectangular photon source ($A = 400 \text{ cm}^2$) emitted photons at a 45° angle relative to the detector's axis, corresponding to the nominal viewing direction of EPHIN aboard SOHO as visualized in the left and middle panel of Fig. 3. During roll conditions, the conditions for the outer ring segments are interchanged (see middle and right panel of the figure). However, for SSD A no further computations are needed. The size of the photon source was chosen so that it illuminates the full Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN). The photon spectrum followed a power law ($I \propto E^{-1}$), resulting in a uniform distribution in logarithmic energy bins in the energy range from 0.003 – 10 MeV with 1 billion photons.

Deposited Energy Distributions: In a first step, the energy loss in all segments of SSD A was computed and is shown in the Fig. 4. It displays in the left and right panels the energy loss in SSD A as a function of photon energy for the full energy range with a threshold of the energy loss in SSD A of 3 and 30 keV, respectively. The lower limit corresponds to the lower energy limit of the computation and the nominal threshold of SSD A, respectively. The histograms illustrate the relation between incident and deposited photon energy. Entries on the diagonal indicate full energy deposition via the photoelectric effect. The influence of the titanium foil above SSD-A becomes visible in the left panel. The vertical band around 4.5 to 5 keV corresponds to the K_α and K_β lines of titanium (for the cross sections see NIST 2025). A curved feature at about 1.7 keV below the diagonal may result from escape peaks.

The right panel covers the energy loss range that is expected to contribute to the count rate of all segments (for the thresholds see Tab. A4). In SSD A secondary electrons and photons may escape the detector for energies above 200 keV causing a lower energy deposition ΔE than E_{in} of the photons. At higher photon energies, the simulation shows Compton edge and pair production signatures as expected. The python code displaying the matrix is available in the tools section of <https://spearhead-he.eu/tools/>.

Figure 3: Panel A and C display a sketch of EPHIN with respect to the viewing directions of the sensor aboard SOHO during nominal and roll conditions, respectively. Panel B shows the orientation of the spacecraft with respect to the Sun during nominal and roll conditions and panel d displays EPHIN's sector distribution with respect to the interplanetary magnetic field. For details on the sensor see text and on the orientation of SOHO see Appendix A2.

Figure 4: Computed energy loss in SSD A ΔE versus input energy E distribution for photons simulated in the energy range from 0.003 MeV to 10 MeV penetrating from the Sun's direction. Note, the different energy loss scales.

Detector Response Functions: As explained by Sullivan (1971) this simulation can be used to obtain the energy response functions $R(E)$ as a function of photon energy E given by:

$$R(E) = G_A \cdot \frac{N_C}{N_A} \quad (6)$$

with $\frac{G_A}{N_A}$ is the photon surface density emitted from the square with side length x, y . A Python tool has been developed to read in the parameters from the macro file used for the computation:

- From `/run/beamOn` we get the number of particles used in the computation. Note, this number needs not to exceed 2^{15} .
- 1-dimensional histograms in energy logarithmic binned in the range given in the macro from `/gps/ene/min` to `/gps/ene/max` with $n + 1$ bins are defined. Both have to be given in MeV.
- The macro also provides the area of the plane:

```
/gps/pos/type Plane
/gps/pos/shape Square
/gps/pos/halfx 10 cm
/gps/pos/halfy 10 cm
```

with $x = 2 \cdot \text{halfx}$ and $y = 2 \cdot \text{halfy}$.

The conditions for incrementing the counter N_C for each segment of SSD A are that one of the 6 segments was hit, and that the energy loss (ioni) is larger than the maximum of the lowest energy and the threshold given.

Detector sensitivity curves for all single segments of SSD A (10 to 15) are displayed in the left, middle and right panels of Fig. 5 for a threshold of 0.003, 0.01 and 0.03 MeV, respectively. The sum of all segments is given by the black curve. The figure shows how efficiently each segment responds to different photon energies. The sensitivity is highest in the range from about 3 keV, with a dip around 5 keV due to titanium absorption NIST (2025). They have a maximum near 9 keV and then they decline as the photoelectric cross-section drops.

Figure 5: From left to right the the energy dependent response function for **SSD A** with an energy threshold of 0.003, 0.01 and 0.030 MeV are shown. For details see text.

At energies > 60 keV, Compton scattering dominates, and above 1 MeV, pair production contributes too. Therefore, the slope of the response function changes and is later increasing with energy. The differences between the segments 1 and 5 and the other segments are caused by the additional shielding of these two segments with respect to the photon source. At higher energies, the production of secondaries sets in, leading to an increase of the other segments. When comparing the different panels of Fig. 5 with each other, the significant differences in the slope from 60 keV to 1 MeV become visible. This is caused by the threshold because of the generation of low energy particles that trigger the low threshold but not the higher ones. These response functions will be utilized in Heber et al. (2025).

The response function for solar photons of **SSD A shows distinct features: Absorption features around 4.5 to 5 keV This feature corresponds to the K_{α} and K_{β} lines of titanium (for the cross sections see NIST 2025).**

Photo effect dominates the response functions between 10 and 60 keV with a strong decrease of sensitivity with photon energy.

Compton scattering and pair production dominate the response from 60 to 1000 keV, and above 1000 keV, respectively.

Instrument shielding: A distinct feature observed is the significant lower response of the segments 1 and 5 with respect to the other ones for thresholds in **SSD A smaller than 30 keV.**

Figure 6: Left: Sketch of SOHO's spacecraft and its instruments (EPHIN's is part of COSTEP suite); Right: The EPHIN model and the spacecraft proxy with a half-sphere aluminum shielding.

2.4.2 Solid State Detector (SSD) F response to cosmic ray radiation

Heber et al. (2015) have shown that EPHIN is capable of monitoring count rate variations with amplitudes in the below 1% regime on an hourly time resolution and hence, observe Forbush Decrease (FD) associated with small Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection (ICME) utilizing the SSD F counts. In Heber et al. (2025) it was shown that these count rates can be used to investigate the GCR proton flux at a rigidity of about 1.33 GV. However, for Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) events these rigidities are far too large, and a detailed knowledge of the response function for electrons, protons and helium is needed. Following Sullivan (1971) the geometric factor of a single detector can be computed using:

$$G = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot A = 2 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot r^2 \quad (7)$$

With $r = 4 \text{ cm}$ the radius of SSD F the geometric factor becomes $G_{\text{SSD}_F} \approx 316 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sr}$.

Influence of the spacecraft environment Although we discuss here only EPHIN aboard SOHO, all other instruments are influenced by the spacecraft shielding: SOHO is equipped with 12 scientific instruments, which are broadly categorized into three groups, including one for in-situ measurements of solar wind and energetic particles. EPHIN's location is shown in the left panel of Fig. 6 with the approximation by a shell model in the right panel:

For a single detector count rate of e.g. SSD F particles from all directions contribute to it. Thus, it is essential to include a model of the spacecraft in the GEANT simulation as described in Köberle et al. (2024):

- As a first step, a simplified model of the spacecraft with given dimensions is implemented in the simulation with the location of the instrument given in the left panel of Fig. 6 for SOHO.
- A simplified "ray tracing" simulation with so-called GEANTINOS was performed to determine the path length for a non-interacting particle passing through the spacecraft. The mass distribution is computed over 4π in steps of 5 degrees.
- This mass distributions are used to scale the density of an aluminum decoy in each given direction. This way, a somewhat "variable thickness" half sphere as a spacecraft proxy was obtained as shown in the right panel of Fig. 6.

Figure 7: Energy response of **SSD-F** for an isotropic flux of protons without (blue curve), including the **SOHO** (green curve) and **Chandra** (red curve) spacecraft, respectively.

This is quite important because **EPHIN** is mounted on one of the edges of the **SOHO** spacecraft, leading to some directions in the field of view being far less obstructed by the passive matter of the spacecraft than others.

Fig. 7 displays the computed energy dependence for protons for **EPHIN** only, aboard the **SOHO** and **Chandra** spacecraft by the blue, green, and red lines, respectively (taken from [Heber et al. 2024b](#)).

The computations were performed using the **GEANT4** Monte Carlo toolkit ([Agostinelli et al. 2003](#)) and the pre-configured geometry of the instrument described in [Köberle et al. \(2024\)](#) with the macro file given in [Appendix A5.2.1](#).

From that figure, it is evident that the minimum proton energy is about 50 MeV to trigger **SSD F** independently of the spacecraft mounting. Below this energy, particles are stopped in the surrounding material. Above ~ 130 MeV (see the dotted vertical red line in Fig. 7), 200 MeV and 300 MeV all trajectories reach **SSD F** for **EPHIN**, **EPHIN** aboard **SOHO** and **Chandra**, respectively. The dotted line gives the geometric factor G for **SSD F** computed as described above. A value in agreement with the geometric factor is found until secondary particle production sets in.

Influence of the energetic particle environment on the **SSD F** count rate

Single-count rate measurements provide data to estimate:

- The energy spectrum of **GCRs**, when combined with the detector sensitivity and the simple one-parameter model provided by the Force Field Solution (**FFS**) ([Moraal 2013](#)).
- The flux of **SEPs** that are energetic particles accelerated by Solar Flares (**SFs**) or Coronal Mass Ejections (**CMEs**) (see for example [Reames 2024](#); [Whitman et al. 2023](#); [Vlahos et al. 2019](#); [Klein & Dalla 2017](#), and references therein).

However, in contrast to differential flux measurements, the chemical composition of the incoming radiation is unknown. While for the investigation of **GCR** modulation, the impact of electrons is negligible (see [Heber et al. 2024a](#)), it is not for **SEP** events. Thus, the response needs to be computed not only for protons, but also for helium and electrons.

Figure 8: Computed response function for SSD F for protons (blue curve), helium (green curve) and electrons (red curve). Note, the different energy scales. For details see text.

The response function of SSD F of SOHO EPHIN shows distinct features:

Absorption by the instrument and spacecraft: The influence of the shielding material are twofold. First the increase of the response function from 0 to the geometric factor computed by the formula given in Sullivan (1971) depends on the shielding and is the highest for the Chandra spacecraft.

Secondary production: The second influence is the production of secondaries with an increase to larger values than the geometric factor.

Particle dependence: The contribution of helium is twice the one from protons for the secondary production. Electrons are counted already at energies from a few MeV so electrons are important during SEP events.

2.4.3 Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN)'s response to penetrating particles

While the previous section discussed the derivation of the response function of single detector counters, we derive in what follows when a complex sensor is used. Like above, EPHIN is used as an example for the derivation of such complex problems. The data frame of the Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN) is grouped by the depth of the particle track in the sensor (see last column in Tab. A2).

Tab. A2 describes the coincidence conditions when EPHIN is run in nominal mode. However, if a detector becomes noisy, the coincidence logic can be changed so that the signal of the corresponding detector is not used. The different failure modes are summarized in section A3.1.

In order to compute the response function, we performed the following steps:

GEANT computations: The GDML macro differs from the one given in section A5.2 in that the sphere is centered around SSD B instead of SSD F for stopping particles, otherwise we keep SSD F. The results utilized in Koeberle et al. (2025) are based on this modification:

```
/gps/pos/centre 0 0 0.0309 cm #centered at SSD B
```

The reason is discussed in the appendix A1 and can be summarized by the imperfect modeling of an isotropic particle environment utilizing the General Particle Source (GPS) cos-distribution on a surface of a sphere with radius R . The systematic uncertainty can be estimated to about 10% if $r = 25$ cm. The input GPS macros used for computing the energy response function of SSD F to penetrating particles can be utilized here for the penetrating ions too because of the inclusion of the spacecraft (see Deliverable Köberle et al. 2024, and references therein).

Instrument characteristics like energy thresholds in the detectors and channel definition are applied to derive "data sets" that can be utilized to compute the response functions.

Validation and systematic uncertainties: In order to validate our Ansatz we applied the method in Heber et al. (2024b) to construct proton flux channels from EPHIN that match the 1 and 1.33 GV channels from AMS 02.

The implementation of EPHIN's counting logic depends on several factors, as discussed above: Several steps are included:

Description of ephin_sim2csv.py

The script is designed to extract the simulation events that contain full detector coverage. The structured Comma-Separated Values (CSV) output is well-suited for further analysis, including data validation and visualization.

Input: The Python script `ephin_sim2csv.py` processes a text file containing simulated EPHIN particle event data. The file contains rows in the following format:

```
# evid det pvekin ioni
1426 100 15.7076 1.3729
1513 40 12.1617 0.0530598
...
```

Each line (excluding those beginning with #) contains:

- `evid`: Event ID
- `det`: Detector number
- `pvekin`: Kinetic energy of the particle
- `ioni`: Ionization value

Processing Steps:

1. The script reads the input file line by line and ignores comment lines.
2. It parses each line into fields and groups data by `evid`, storing all measurements associated with the same event ID.
3. A fixed list of required detector IDs is defined as:

```
detectors = [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 30, 40, 50, 60, 100]
```

4. An event is retained only if it contains at least one entry for each of the 17 required detectors.
5. Events with missing detectors or only detector ids not in the list are discarded.

Output Format Each valid event is written to a single CSV line is written in the following format:

```
det10 det11 det12 det13 det14 det15 det20 det21 det22 det23 det24 det25 det30 det40 det50 det60 det100 evid ekin
```

This results in:

- 17 columns for the energy losses in MeV in one detector (each segment of the SSD 1 and 2 are counted as a detector)
- The event identification and the input energy in MeV

```
#det10 det11 det12 det13 det14 det15 det20 det21 det22 det23 det24 det25 det30 det40 det50 det60 det100 evid ekin
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 2.2965 3 17.0765
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 1.66594 13 20.9132
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 39 14.0621
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 2.60577 6.16597 0.0 0.0 1.04827 41 21.1744
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 2.63006 43 22.0628
```



```
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.409567 0.741971 47 22.7713
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.234786 0.0 58 19.5659
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 60 17.4296
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 1.27766 69 13.1959
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0150368 112 19.5662
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 4.04148 199 16.4811
```

Description of coincidences.py

The script `coincidences.py` analyzes a simulation output file from the `ephin_sim2csv.py` script. Each row in the input file corresponds to a single simulated particle event, with energy depositions and ionization values combined across detectors for that event.

The primary goal of the script is to identify and classify **coincidence patterns** given in Tab. A2 of the EPHIN detectors above the predefined energy loss thresholds given in Tab. A4, i.e., to determine which sets of detectors are simultaneously triggered by energy deposition from simulated particles in agreement with Tab. A2. These patterns help evaluate detector response characteristics. Also implemented are the changes due to the FM E and FM D and the influence of switching of the outer segments of the Solid State Detector (SSD) A and B.

The input file must be an output file from the `ephin_sim2csv.py` script:

1. The script `coincidences.py` reads the simulation data from the specified CSV file.
2. It applies a set of fixed ionization thresholds per detector to determine whether that detector was triggered.
3. Based on triggered detectors, it constructs a **coincidence pattern**—a set of detectors that responded in the event. Note that the validity depends on the flag if FM E or FM E and FM D or the outer segments of SSDs A and B were switched on or off.
4. If a valid event is recorded the associated energy deposition as well as the coincidence type, the segment in SSD A and B for further analysis.
5. The output is saved in a CSV file summarizing all coincidence patterns and their characteristics:

```
# failuremode: none
# ring: on
# coinc depth segA segB A B C D E F pvekin event_id
12 6 5 5 0.121741 0.0829302 1.23432 1.8462 1.88361 0.610965 13.7656 6560
12 6 1 2 0.0565911 0.0992748 1.03014 1.83208 3.37428 0.214719 16.8991 8880
12 6 4 4 0.0401034 0.0840012 1.26115 1.8248 1.95575 0.240074 15.5855 9211
```

The script supports the following command-line options:

- `-file FILE`
Path to the input simulation file (required).
- `-fm FM`
Specifies the **failure mode** configuration of the detectors to be considered. This simulates various operational states or malfunctions.
Options:
 - `none` (default) – all detectors function normally.

- `fme` – failure of detector E.
- `fmd_fme` – failure of detectors D and E.
- `-ring RING`
Specifies whether the **ring configuration** is used in the simulation. This may affect how detector triggers are interpreted.
Options:
 - `off`
 - `on`

responses.py Script

The `responses.py` script is designed to compute and optionally plot the response functions of various particle detection channels (coincidences) based on Monte Carlo simulation data. It processes energy spectra from a coincidence data file generated by the `coincidences.py` script and normalizes the results using simulation parameters defined in the corresponding macro configuration file. The main features of the python code are:

- Parses a macro configuration file for simulation parameters.
- Reads coincidence energy data and bins it into histograms.
- Calculates response functions for selected coincidence channels.
- Optionally generates plots for visual analysis.
- Exports results to a JSON file for further use.

Function Descriptions:

load_simulation_params (macro_path): Parses a Geant4-style macro file and extracts a limited set of allowed parameters such as:

- `/gps/ene/min, /gps/ene/max`: Energy range
- `/gps/pos/radius`: Source radius
- `/run/beamOn`: Number of particles simulated

The script exits if `/gps/ene/alpha` is not equal to `-1`.

generate_histograms (bins, coins, coinc_data_path) Reads a text file containing energy and coincidence data. For each selected coincidence type, it builds a histogram of the primary particle's kinetic energy (`pvekin`) using logarithmic binning.

convert_for_json (obj): Recursively converts NumPy arrays and other non-serializable types into JSON-compatible formats.

When enabled, the script produces log-log plots of the response functions. Coincidence channels are grouped as:

- **Electrons:** Channels 0–3
- **Protons:** Channels 4–7
- **Alphas:** Channels 8–11
- **Integral:** Channel 12

The computed responses are stored in a `.json` file that can be used for further analysis.

Table 1: Upper table: AMS-02 channels used in our analysis. Lower table: Energy ranges utilized for the comparison with AMS-02 from EPHIN

AMS Energy channel/GV	E_l/MeV	E_u/MeV		
1	433	554		
1.4	554	690		
$\Delta E_l/(\text{MeV}/\text{mm})$	$\Delta E_u/(\text{MeV}/\text{mm})$	E_{eff}/MeV	$R/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr})$	Segment
0.45	0.52	679.	64.4	$A = B = 0$
0.52	0.64	505.	56.1	$A = B = 0$
0.45	0.52	743.	1626.3	all
0.52	0.64	539.	1293.5	all
0.45	0.52	699.	404.1	$A_i = B_i$
0.52	0.64	523.	337.0	$A_i = B_i$
0.45	0.52	735.	410.8	$B = 0$
0.52	0.64	529.	323.9	$B = 0$

2.4.4 Results

Penetrating protons: Utilizing the above chain, we computed in deliverable Heber et al. (2024b) the energy ranges to be comparable with the AMS rigidity channels at 1 and 1.3 GV summarized in Tab. 1 (from Heber et al. 2024b). The corresponding response functions are shown in the upper panel of Fig. 9. The response function shown in the lower panel is used to define the above 100 MeV protons utilized in deliverable D5.1 (Vainio et al. 2024).

Figure 9: The top and bottom panels display the response functions utilized in [Heber et al. \(2024b\)](#) and in [Vainio et al. \(2024\)](#), respectively.

Figure 10: From left to right are shown the energies response of EPHIN's "highest" electron channels during nominal, FM E and FM E and FM D conditions (for details see text).

MeV electrons: Utilizing the above chain, we computed in deliverable [Koeberle et al. \(2025\)](#) the efficient energies for the highest electron channels measured by EPHIN. Note, in 1997 and 2017, EPHIN was switched to failure modes E and D, respectively. This means that detectors D and E are excluded from any coincidence logic due to the increased noise levels in these detectors. Due to the loss of the two detectors, the original Level-2 channels have been successfully replaced by a Level-3 data set (see for details [Kühl et al. 2017](#), and references therein) for protons and helium. In contrast to ions for which the full energy range coverage can be recovered using the energy loss ΔE in the different detectors, for electrons only two and one energy channel(s) remain for which a higher energy resolution can be obtained. The energy range towards the highest electron energies is substantially reduced when switching to FMs E and D. To quantify the effect, the above chain has been applied resulting in the response functions shown in Fig. 10. Only a few events in 1996 and 1997 were measured during nominal conditions we applied to the data analysis performed in [Koeberle et al. \(2025\)](#) only the latter two that correspond to energies of ~ 1 MeV.

2.5 ERNE aboard SOHO

2.5.1 The ERNE HED instrument

The Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron (ERNE) experiment (Valtonen et al. 1997) is one of the scientific payloads aboard SOHO. The instrument layout of ERNE's High Energy Detector (HED) is illustrated in Fig. 11. At the top are the silicon strip detectors S1x, S1y, S2x, and S2y, each with a thickness of 300 μm . Each layer contains two chips, each measuring 40.4 mm \times 81.9 mm, resulting in a combined active geometric area of approximately 46 cm².

Beneath the strip detectors lies the D1 detector, composed of two silicon layers, each 500 μm thick, making the total thickness 1000 μm . Below D1 is the D2 layer, a CsI(Tl) scintillator with an active area of 79.5 mm \times 79.5 mm and a thickness of 8 mm.

Figure 11: A sketch of the ERNE-HED sensor head.

Following downward from D2 is the D3 detector, which consists of five BGO scintillator bars, each with dimensions of 15.4 mm \times 15.0 mm \times 79.5 mm. Surrounding the detector stack are the anticoincidence detectors, made of plastic scintillator plates with a thickness of 5.2 mm. These include two logical anticoincidence detectors: AC1, located at the bottom of the stack, and AC2, positioned along the sides of D2 and D3.

ERNE HED model We reconstructed the SOHO / ERNE model using the paper drawings archive. Each mechanical part of the instrument was sketched as a 3-D body in the mechanical Computer-Aided Design (CAD) software. When all parts were completed, the instrument was digitally assembled into a realistic CAD model with assigned materials. The model was tessellated and converted into GDML. The conversion engine is pyg4ometry (Walker et al. 2022; Boogert et al. 2025).

SOHO spacecraft model In addition to the instrument head, we reconstructed a 3-D model of the SOHO spacecraft. We will use the same method as described above in Sect. 2.4.2 to construct a shield (like the one shown in Fig. 6) equivalent to the passive structure surrounding the sensitive head of the instrument. We aim to represent the spacecraft as a compact spherical shell with a thickness corresponding to the amount of passive spacecraft material. Currently, the GDML model of SOHO is prepared for geantino scanning as illustrated in Fig. 12.

Figure 12: A GEANT4 visualisation of the SOHO spacecraft model with ERNE onboard. In the right panel, the yellow piece on the top with red spots is the ERNE sensor unit.

2.5.2 Response functions of ERNE HED

We calculated the responses of two penetrating particle counters of ERNE. Each counter requires an EVENT condition, which is a combination of three valid (single-segment) hits in the position-sensitive layers S1y, S2x, and S2y (see Fig. 11), a hit in the bottom anticoincidence detector AC1, and no hit in the side anticoincidence detectors AC2. The C5 counter, in addition, requires the deposit in the D1 layer to be above 1.3 MeV.

As the AC1 energy deposit threshold is not well known, we simulated a set of response functions with feasible AC1 threshold levels. Figure 13 shows the response functions for particles penetrating the whole ERNE sensor head incident from the aperture.

Figure 13: GEANT4 simulated responses of ERNE AC counters for forward penetrating relativistic protons.

As the first step towards the characterisation of the spacecraft shielding effect (see Sect. 2.5.1) on the response functions of ERNE, we placed a roughly equivalent uniform slab of ultra-dense aluminium below the ERNE HED model. We simulated the response to backwards-penetrating particles. The response functions are shown in Fig. 14.

Figure 14: GEANT4 simulated responses of ERNE AC counters for backward penetrating relativistic protons.

2.6 SoIO/HET response

2.6.1 The HET Instrument

HET was designed to cover the high energy range for electrons, protons and also for several heavy ion species from $E \approx 7$ MeV/nuc to $E \approx 500$ MeV/nuc for ions that stop in the sensor head (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020). Two Electron Proton Telescope (EPT)-HET units, Flight Model (FMO)1 and FMO2, are mounted on the Solar Orbiter spacecraft with FMO1 looking in sun/antisun direction along the average Parker spiral and FMO2 pointing out of the ecliptic.

Figure 15 shows a sketch of the HET instrument with exemplary particle trajectories for different coincidence conditions. Of special interest due to their large geometric factors for the highly energetic particles studied within SPEARHEAD are the so called GCR trigger channels shown in aquamarine, requiring a coincidence of only the inner or middle B segments and the C detector, and the single detector counters shown in orange. Both come with two subchannels, which are detailed in the subsequent section.

Figure 15: Schematic diagram of the HET sensor head. Exemplary particle trajectories ending up in different data products are shown by the arrows: stopping in B (red), stopping in C (green), penetrating (blue), GCR channel (aquamarine), C single counter (orange). From (Freiherr von Forstner et al. 2021)

2.6.2 GEANT simulations of the HET

The GEANT4 model as detailed in Köberle et al. (2024) has been developed implementing all distances and dimensions of the instrument from the CAD data, which was used for the manufacturing of the individual parts of the instrument. The simulation includes the fully equipped sensor and the electronic box of the EPT-HET unit (see left panel of Fig. 16) as well as a spacecraft model (see right panel of 16).

Here of special interest is the so called GCR trigger. As Fig. 15 illustrates the trigger conditions and a possible trajectory of a particle counted in the GCR channel, a particle is counted in the channel if a coincidence in the inner segments of the two B detectors and a signal in the BGO-crystal is present.

The simulation for SoIO/HET was performed for protons, alpha particles, and electrons in the energy range between 1 MeV and 100 GeV.

Figure 17 shows the respective response functions for the single detector counter that measures the signal in the BGO without any further coincidence condition. The single detector counter provides two channels that are defined by the energy loss thresholds at 4 MeV(High Gain (HG)) and 10 MeV(Low Gain (LG)). It can be seen that the response functions for each species follow roughly the same shape, with the main differences in the low energy cutoff, where electrons can be measured just above the thresholds, whereas the response functions for protons and alpha particles start to rise at 12 and 45 MeV, respectively, for the energy loss threshold of 4 MeV. Toward higher energies, the production of secondary particles in the spacecraft results in an increase of the response functions. This effect is

Figure 16: GEANT4 visualization of the HET sensor head and electronic box and HET sensor head with spacecraft model of SoIo in the left and right panel, respectively.

especially profound for alpha particles and electrons, showing a response $\approx 2x$ that of protons at 100 GeV.

Figure 17: Simulation results for single detector response functions of protons, alphas and electrons for detection thresholds of 4 and 10 MeV deposited in the BGO with spacecraft model.

Figure 18 shows simulation results of the GCR trigger for protons, alpha particles, and electrons. Again, two channels are given by energy loss intervals in the BGO between 15 to 30 MeV and 30 to 56 MeV. These channels are indicated GCR-0 and GCR-1, respectively. As can be seen, the GCR trigger are predominantly sensitive to protons where the response remains close to the analytical geometry factor marked as black dashed horizontal line at energies above the cutoff at ≈ 140 MeV. The two response functions of the channels intersect at 350 MeV. The increase in the response functions of alpha particles and electrons at energies > 1 GeV due to the spacecraft is considered to be negligible.

Figure 18: Simulation results for GCR trigger response functions of protons, alphas and electrons in two channels of 15 to 30 and 30 to 56 MeV deposited in the BGO with spacecraft model. The horizontal dashed line marks the analytical geometry factor. For clarity, the legend, valid for all panels, is only shown in the middle panel.

2.7 Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer (SIXS) aboard BepiColombo

2.7.1 The SIXS-P instrument

The SIXS-P particle instrument (Huovelin et al. 2020) consists of five planar silicon detectors with a thickness of 150 μm around a $5 \times 5 \times 6.3 \text{ mm}^3$ CsI(Tl) parallelepiped scintillation crystal. All silicon detectors have a central round active area in the center and a square anticoincidence area surrounding the active spot. The silicon detectors and the scintillator are housed in an aluminum collimator dome, as shown in Fig. 19. SIXS-P implements the ΔE -E method of particle identification.

Figure 19: The SIXS-P detector head (from Huovelin et al. 2020, Fig. 8).

The cruise configuration During the cruise phase, the field of view of SIXS-P is partially obstructed by the spacecraft structure. Magnetospheric Orbiter Sunshield and Interface (MOSIF) partially shades Side 0 and fully obstructs the field of view of Side 4. In the cruise data, the flux in Side 0 could be corrected for shading by applying a division by 0.8. The MOSIF structure (see Fig. 20) absorbs most protons within the nominal energy range of SIXS-P. Electrons are scattered by the upper layers of MOSIF and partially detected by Side 4. Nevertheless, Side 4 shall not be used until the orbital phase starts.

SIXS-P instrument model The GEANT4 render of the GDML model of the SIXS-P detector head is shown in the right panel of Fig. 21. The model has been improved by including the immediate spacecraft structures, as shown in the left panel of Fig. 21.

2.7.2 Particle response functions of SIXS-P

We calculated the responses of SIXS-P to protons and electrons. We also analyzed the contamination caused by protons and electrons in respective contaminated channels (e.g., cosmic ray protons in electron channels).

Figure 20: BepiColombo Mercury Magnetospheric Orbiter Sunshield and Interface (MOSIF) that partially shades the field of view of SIXS-P. Photo credit ESA.

Figure 21: A GEANT4 visualization of the SIXS instrument model.

Figure 22: GEANT4 simulated response functions of SIXS-P to protons.

Figure 23: GEANT4 simulated response functions of SIXS-P to electrons.

Protons The left panel of Fig. 22 shows the response of Side 0 to protons in the proton channels of SIXS-P. The right panel of Fig. 22 shows the cross-species response of Side 0 in the electron channels of SIXS-P and the assessment of how the "O" or "Other" channel responds to high-energy protons.

Electrons The left panel of Fig. 23 shows the response of Side 0 to electrons in the electron channels of SIXS-P. The right panel of Fig. 23 shows electron contamination in the first three, lowest energy, proton channels.

2.7.3 Photon response of SIXS-P

We also simulated the photon response functions of SIXS-P for X-ray energies in the range of 30–300 keV using the GEANT4 model described above. We simulated the effective area of photon detection for a parallel beam of photons, varying both the zenith and azimuth (i.e., phase) angles with respect to the normal of Side 0 detector. The phase angle is measured from the direction between the sides 1 and 2. The results for the vertical incidence are presented in Fig. 24. We present the results for both the Side 0 detector and the other ones that are at 90-degree angle with respect to Side 0. The active area of the detector element is $4.9 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2$. As can be seen, the effective area at low energies is lower than the physical size of the detector, but increases above the physical size once the energy exceeds about 250 keV. This is because secondary radiation can be generated in the tantalum collimator rings of the instrument. We can see that there is a broad minimum in active area around 100 keV photon energy, with the secondary radiation kicking in at higher energies.

Examples of the effective area in other beam orientations are given in Fig. 25. The phase angle

Figure 24: Effective area for photon detection of SIXS-P for a parallel beam normal to the Side 0 detector. The curve labeled "top" gives the Side 0 detector response, and the other curves depict the response of side detectors perpendicular to Side 0.

direction has an effect in the detectors that are perpendicular to Side 0. The response depends on the amount of dead material between the detector active area and space, which decreases the effective area for low photon energies because of absorption, but increases the effective area at high photon energies because of secondary radiation production.

Figure 26 shows the effective area broken down to the electron channel responses for the vertical incidence of Side 0. The sharp lower-energy edges of the responses depict the energy channel limits in detected energies. As is evident, incident photon energies in many cases are larger than the measured energies of the channel, resulting from Compton scattering.

The computed counting rates for these effective areas are low, as shown in Heber et al. (2025). Experimental verification of the active areas has to wait until the mission arrives at Mercury (November 2026) to have visibility to the Sun.

Figure 25: Effective area for photon detection of SIXS-P for a parallel beam at given zenith and phase angle with respect to the Side 0 detector normal. The curves labeled "top" give the Side 0 detector response, and the other curves depict the responses of the side detectors perpendicular to Side 0.

Figure 26: Effective area for photon detection of SIXS-P for a parallel beam normal to the Side 0 detector, broken down to responses of the individual electron energy channels.

3 Summary and Conclusions

This deliverable describes the implementation and application of **GEANT4** simulations for a set of particle detectors used in space missions: **SOHO/Chandra EPHIN**, **SOHO-ERNE**, **SoIO-HET**, and **BepiColombo-SIXS**. The work applies the **Sullivan (1971)** formalism to compute detector response functions, integrating realistic **GDML**-based geometry, spacecraft shielding, and energy thresholds. The approach consists of four steps: (1) creating a **GDML** model of the instrument, (2) utilizing the **GEANT (GPS)** for controlling the Monte Carlo simulations of particle interactions, (3) extracting energy depositions and channel counts, and (4) validating results against in-flight data. Specific examples include **EPHIN's SSD A** response to photons, **SSD F's** response to cosmic ray protons, and **EPHIN's** response to penetrating particles (including consideration of Failure Mode (**FM**) scenarios). Similar analyses were performed for **SOHO-ERNE**, **SoIO-HET**, and **BepiColombo-SIXS**.

Results The **GEANT4** simulations produce response functions for photons, protons, helium nuclei, and electrons across a range of energies. **SSD A's** results reveal distinct photoabsorption features and sensitivity variations due to thresholds and shielding. **SSD F's** response captures the effects of spacecraft shielding and particle generation of secondaries, yielding realistic estimates for **GCRs** and **SEP** events. The **EPHIN** results enable the construction of channel response matrices for multi-layer detection modes, including their behaviour in **FM** conditions. The **HET** results demonstrate that **GCR** triggers closely match the theoretical geometry factor, with low-energy cut-offs defined by spacecraft shielding. These results have been used for cross-calibration with **AMS-02** data and to define standard channels for multi-instrument particle studies.

We successfully applied the sensor geometry and the spacecraft environment in a Virtual Machine (VM) that runs a pre-installed version of GEANT4 for SOHO and Chandra EPHIN, SOHO ERNE, SoIO HET, and BepiColombo SIXS. A robust set of response functions and validated models that enable accurate particle flux derivation across a range of spacecraft instruments were computed and will be provided via the SPEARHEAD website as well as on <https://zenodo.org>. These response functions were applied as input to the bow-tie tool described in Gieseler et al. (2024) for example in Vainio et al. (2024), Koeberle et al. (2025) and Heber et al. (2024b).

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Appendix

A1 Geometric Requirement for Isotropic Emission Toward a Cylindrical Detector

In [GEANT4](#), an isotropic distribution of particles within a spherical volume can be simulated using the General Particle Source ([GPS](#)) module by:

- Defining a spherical surface as the origin of the particles (using the `GPS /gps/pos/type Surface` and `/gps/pos/shape Sphere` commands).
- Setting a specific radius for the sphere from which particles will be emitted.
- Using the `/gps/ang/type iso` command to emit particles isotropically from the surface.
- Ensuring only particles directed inward (i.e., into the sphere) are considered. This is done by restricting the angular emission to the inward hemisphere relative to the radial surface normal.

Mathematically, the condition for inward direction is:

$$\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{r} < 0$$

where \mathbf{v} is the velocity (momentum direction) of the particle and \mathbf{r} is the position vector from the center of the sphere to the emission point.

This approach ensures that the resulting distribution of particles inside the sphere is spatially isotropic, despite particles only being launched from the boundary surface.

Only directions with $\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{r} < 0$ are accepted

Figure 27: Illustration of the setup to generate an isotropic flux within a sphere with starting points on the surface of the sphere and inward-pointing vectors: solid lines point toward the center; dotted lines are inward but off-center.

Isotropic distribution

However, the above solution does provide isotropy only very close to the center of the sphere, but our experiments can be approximated by cylinders within the sphere, as illustrated in [Fig. 28](#). To estimate the minimum radius R of a spherical particle source surrounding a cylindrical detector such that the directional deviation from perfect isotropic illumination of the cylinder is less than 10%.

The cylindrical detector has:

- Radius r

Cylinder inside a spherical particle source

Figure 28: Illustration of the geometry used to compute the energy response within WP 2.

- Height Z

The particles are emitted isotropically from the surface of a sphere with radius R , centered along the axis of the cylinder.

Geometric Considerations

To minimize the angular bias, the solid angle subtended by the cylinder from any point on the source sphere must remain nearly constant. For this, the sphere must be sufficiently distant, such that directional variations are small.

The effective angular span seen from a point on the sphere to the edge of the cylinder is given approximately by:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{r}{Z/2} \right) \Rightarrow \sin(\theta) \approx \frac{r}{\sqrt{r^2 + (Z/2)^2}}$$

The variation in incident angles translates to a deviation in flux uniformity. To keep this below 10%, the distance from source to cylinder must satisfy:

$$\frac{r}{R} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2 + (Z/2)^2}} < 0.1$$

Solving for R :

$$R > \frac{r}{0.1 \cdot \sqrt{r^2 + (Z/2)^2}}$$

A2 SOHO's nominal Attitude Control and Roll

The Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) maintained a three-axis stabilized attitude with the spacecraft's +Z axis (the High Gain Antenna and instrument boresight) pointing at the Sun. Nominal attitude control was achieved using a set of three gyroscopes, star trackers, and Sun sensors.

Roll control, specifically, was maintained by:

- Integrating angular rate information from the gyroscopes.
- Correcting accumulated errors via star tracker updates.
- Executing planned roll maneuvers via reaction wheels and thrusters to maintain instrument alignment.

1998 Anomaly and Loss of Attitude

In June 1998, a series of errors led to:

- Loss of two gyroscopes (A and C) due to a failed calibration procedure.
- Deactivation of the only healthy gyro (B).
- Multiple entries into Emergency Sun Reacquisition (ESR) mode.
- A rapid and uncontrolled increase in roll rate.

As a result, SOHO entered a tumbling state, losing both Sun pointing and telemetry by June 25, 1998.

Gyroless Recovery and Roll Reconstruction

Between August 3 and September 16, 1998, a phased recovery was executed using:

- **Sun sensors** to re-establish coarse attitude.
- **Fine Sun-pointing via star trackers.**
- **Thrust vector control** (hydrazine thrusters) to control pitch and yaw using solar limb centering algorithms.
- **Roll determination** from star tracker data by matching field-of-view stars to known star maps.

Eventually, attitude control was restored without gyroscopes by using:

- **Software-based attitude estimation** combining Sun sensor and star tracker data.
- **Modified on-board control laws** to emulate gyroscopic functions with frequent star tracker updates.

Because of communication issues, the spacecraft needs to be operated regularly in a roll position. A detailed description is found in [NASA/ESA \(1998\)](#).

A3 The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN)

The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN, Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) is part of the COSTEP suite onboard SOHO. A schematic view of the EPHIN instrument is shown in Panel A of Fig. 3. The instrument consists of a stack of six SSDs (labeled A-F in Fig. 3) that is surrounded by a scintillation detector (G), which acts as an anticoincidence. SSDs A and B are divided into six segments, with all of them having the same volume. The dimensions and the energy resolutions for the SSDs are summarized in Tab. A3 and the coincidence logic in Tab. A2.

Since the data rate is limited, energy losses in detectors A-E can only be transmitted for a statistical ensemble of all particles counted by EPHIN. A crude separation between electrons, protons, and helium has been introduced for different penetration depths, that is, different coincidences, by introducing different energy-loss thresholds in SSD A (summarized in Tab. A4 and detailed in Müller-Mellin et al. 1995). To monitor time-dependent instrumental issues, various parameters are recorded independently of any coincidence condition, including the sensor and electronic box temperatures, leakage currents, but also the count rates of the six SSDs (A to F) and the anticoincidence scintillator (G) of EPHIN. The review by Vilmer (2005) highlights that the energy spectra of X-ray and gamma-ray emissions during SEP-associated solar flares exhibit substantial variability. Hard X-rays show power-law spectra with time-dependent spectral indices, often evolving from hard to soft or vice versa during the flare, reflecting changes in acceleration and trapping of electrons. Thus, the focus of Heber et al. (2025) is on expected count rates for specific events, the influence of the energy threshold, and the behavior of individual detector segments.

Table A2: Predefined coincidence channels used by EPHIN. Adapted from (Müller-Mellin et al. 1995).

Type	Name	Energy Range		Coincidence Condition ⁶	Note	Depth
		MeV/nuc				
		Low	High			
Electron	E150	0.15	0.7	$A0 \overline{A1} B0 \overline{C0} \overline{D0} \overline{E0} \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	4,5	2
	E300	0.67	3.0	$A0 \overline{A1} B0 C0 \overline{D0} \overline{E0} \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	1,4,5	3
	E1300	2.64	7.8	$A0 \overline{A1} B0 C0 D0 \overline{E0} \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	1,4,5	4
	E3000	4.80	10.4	$A0 \overline{A1} B0 C0 D0 E0 \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	1,4,5	5
Proton	P4	4.3	7.8	$A1 \overline{A4} B0 \overline{C0} \overline{D0} \overline{E0} \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$		2
	P8	7.8	25.0	$A1 \overline{A3} B0 C0 \overline{D0} \overline{E0} \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	2	3
	P25	25.0	40.9	$A1 \overline{A3} B0 C0 D0 \overline{E0} \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	2	4
	P42	40.9	53.0	$A1 \overline{A3} B0 C0 D0 E0 \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	2	5
Helium	H4	4.3	7.8	$A4 \overline{A4} B0 \overline{C0} \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$		2
	H8	7.8	25.0	$A3 \overline{A3} B0 C0 \overline{D0} \overline{E0} \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	3	3
	H25	25.0	40.9	$A2 \overline{A3} B0 C0 D0 \overline{E0} \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	3	4
	H42	40.9	53.0	$A2 \overline{A3} B0 C0 D0 E0 \overline{F0} \overline{G0}$	3	5
Integral	Electrons	8.7	∞	$A0 B0 C0 F0 \overline{G0}$	4	6
	Nucleons	53.0				

¹ : Today, the original channels E300, E1300 and E3000 are combined due to the failures of detectors D and E.

² : Today, the original channels P8, P24 and P42 are combined due to the failures of detectors D and E.

³ : Today, the original channels H8, H24 and H42 are combined due to the failures of detectors D and E.

⁴ : The upper energy limits for electron channels are not hard cuts.

⁵ : The electron energy losses are in MeV.

⁶ : A0 denotes an energy threshold that needs to be passed, $\overline{A1}$ a threshold that may not be passed. The threshold values can be found in Müller-Mellin et al. (1995).

Table A3: Detector Specifications (adapted from Müller-Mellin et al. 1995).

Detector	A	B	C	D,E	F
Type	ion-implanted	ion-implanted	Lithium-drifted	Lithium-drifted	ion-implanted
Thickness [μm]	150 ± 10	300 ± 15	3000 ± 10	5000 ± 10	700 ± 15
Active Area [mm^2]	1130	1130	1500	1500	5000
Number of Segments	6	6	1	1	1
α -Res. keV FWHM	36	36	≤ 150	≤ 150	80
β -Res. keV FWHM	12	12	–	–	70

Table A4: Discriminator thresholds of the EPHIN flight unit at +20 °C. The threshold of the anticoincidence detector G is set at $G_0 = 1.60$ pC (corresponding to an energy loss of approximately 100 keV), with a temperature coefficient of $-T = -4.4$ fC/K. The analog channels and discriminator thresholds of the segments of detectors A and B are matched to better than 1%. (The temperature coefficients $-T$ are the result of temperature tests conducted between 0 and +50 °C). Table adapted from (Sierks 1997). The ID gives the number in the output files from the GEANT 4 simulations with $i = 0, 5$ for SSD A and B segments.

Detector	Threshold [keV]	$-T$ [eV/K]	ID	Detector	Threshold [keV]	$-T$ [eV/K]	ID
A0	30	-120	1i	B0	60	-50	2i
A1	270	-70		C0	359	-260	30
A2	973	-230		D0	581	-340	40
A3	2000	-800		E0	582	-260	50
A4	5320	-2200		F0	150	-60	60
				G0	150		100

A3.1 Description of EPHIN's Failure Mode Design

Semiconductor detectors are sensitive components. They can fail by either growing noisy or turning dead. Both cases can jeopardize the instrument logic of a particle telescope. In order to recover from such a situation, the EPHIN onboard coincidence logic can be reconfigured by telecommand (see Table A5).

Table A5: Signals generated by Failure Mode Reconfiguration

Failing Detector	Failure Mode	Generated Threshold Signal
A (all segments)	FMA	AF00 := 1 (only central segment)
B (all segments)	FMB	BF00 := 1 (only central segment)
C	FMC	C0 := 1
D	FMD	D0 := C0
E	FME	E0 := F0
F	FMF	F0 := 0

Note: The generated threshold signal cannot trigger the coincidence recognition cycle.

By way of this failure mode reconfiguration, the signals of the good detectors can still be analyzed and registered in the allotted coincidence counters (see Table A6).

Table A6: Resulting Coincidence Assignment for FMD+FME

If the particle reaches	it will be counted in
B	E150 or P4 or H4 (No change)
C, but not F	E1300 or P25 or H25 (Assumed to stop in D)
F	INT (No change)

Predicted Consequence for Counting Rates

The combined effect of FMD+FME on coincidence counters is summarized in Table A7.

Predicted Consequence for Pulse Height Words

Table A8 shows the effect on pulse height words, including the impact of an uploaded program patch to recover detector E pulse amplitudes.

Table A7: Effect of FMD+FME on Coincidence Counters

Coincidence Counters	Effect
E150, P4, H4, INT	Not affected
E300, P8, H8	Counting zero
E1300, P25, H25	Counting more due to larger energy window
E3000, P41, H41	Counting zero

Table A8: Effect of FMD+FME and Patch on Pulse Height Words

Coincidence Type	Effect
E150, P4, H4	Not affected
E300, P8, H8, E1300, P25, H25	No PHA words
E3000, P41, H41	PHA_D = 0 and PHA_E = 0 for good E300, P8, H8 PHA_D > 0 and PHA_E = 0 for good E1300, P25, H25 PHA_D > 0 and PHA_E > 0 for good E3000, P41, H41

A4 Validation of the **GEANT** model of an Energetic Particle Instruments

1. Characterization of Detector Response

Pre-flight Characterization: Before launch the detector response is characterized using well-known particle sources in controlled environments. Single Solid State Detector (**SSD**) of the **EPHIN** were irradiated with radioactive isotopes. The full telescope was calibrated with different ions from hydrogen to Lithium at the Hahn Meitner Institut (**HMI**) in Berlin and with electrons at the accelerator in Gent (for details see [Sierks 1997](#), and the appendix ??).

Efficiency calibration: This involves determining the probability that the instrument detects an incident particle of a given type and energy. It often requires detailed modeling of the detector geometry and material interactions using software like **GEANT4** ([Agostinelli et al. 2003](#)).

Geometric Factor Calculation: The response and geometric factor quantify the effective areas of the detector through which the particles are counted. This parameter depends on the instrument design, including the field of view and the acceptance angle ([Sullivan 1971](#)). The most simple case is the case of a single **SSD** for which the solution is analytically derived in [Sullivan \(1971\)](#).

2. On-orbit Calibration and Monitoring

In-flight Calibration: After launch, calibration needs to be periodically checked using e.g. the energy loss of Minimum Ionizing Particles (**MIPs**) (see for example [Heber 1997](#), who applied this criteria to Ulysses Kiel Electron Telescope (**KET**) measurements).

Cross-calibration: Instruments may also be cross-calibrated against other well-characterized instruments operating on the same mission or nearby platforms. Here we utilize published data from **AMS-02** ([Heber et al. 2024b](#)).

3. Background and Noise Characterization

Noise Reduction: Understanding the noise characteristics (thermal noise, electronic noise) of the instrument is essential for accurately interpreting low-energy loss particle events (see deliverable [Heber et al. 2025](#)).

Background Radiation: Instruments are exposed to cosmic rays and other high-energy particles, contributing to the background signal. Calibration procedures include background subtraction or mitigation strategies.

4. Data Analysis and Calibration Correction

Spectral Unfolding: For instruments that measure an integrated response over an energy range, unfolding techniques are applied to derive the true energy spectrum of the particles from the measured data (see for example [Gieseler et al. 2024](#), and references therein).

Dead-Time Correction: The finite processing time of the detector can lead to missed events, especially in high-flux environments. Calibration must account for this dead time effect (see for example [Sierks 1997](#)).

A5 Macros used in the simulation

A5.1 Photon computation

A5.1.1 Geometry Description Markup Language (GDML) file

```
# Which GDML file to use

/gdml/file /home/local1/G4VM/EPHIN/ephin_soho_shield.gdml

# Physics based parameters
/run/setCut 0.001 mm

# Random and machine parameters
/random/setSeeds 5544293 7121843
/run/numberOfThreads 1

# Initialization of program

/run/initialize

# Define Output

/run/verbose 0
/event/verbose 0
/tracking/verbose 0
/sd/verbose 1
/sd/format evid det pvekin ioni
/sd/file output1/soho/eph-soho-photons-high

#Define source parameters

#particle type

/gps/particle gamma

# particle energy distribution

/gps/ene/type Pow
/gps/ene/alpha -1
/gps/ene/min 3 keV
/gps/ene/max 10 MeV

# Source and direction

/gps/pos/type Plane
/gps/pos/shape Square
/gps/pos/centre 15. 0. -10. cm
/gps/pos/halfx 10 cm
/gps/pos/halfy 10 cm
```



```
/gps/pos/rot1 1 0 1
/gps/direction -1 0 1

# number of particles

/run/beamOn 1000000000
```

A5.1.2 Python code used to plot the energy loss vs. energy matrix and the responses

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
"""
Updated on May 22, 2025
Plots photon simulation histograms for a range of detectors, specified via command-line.
Includes a 2D histogram and 1D line-style histograms per detector, plus a summed curve.
"""

import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from matplotlib.colors import LogNorm
import argparse

# Set global font sizes for plots
plt.rcParams.update({
    'font.size': 14,
    'axes.titlesize': 16,
    'axes.labelsize': 14,
    'xtick.labelsize': 12,
    'ytick.labelsize': 12,
    'legend.fontsize': 12
})

# Parse command-line arguments
parser = argparse.ArgumentParser(description="Plot photon simulation histograms for a range of f
parser.add_argument("det_min", type=int, help="Minimum detector number (inclusive)")
parser.add_argument("det_max", type=int, help="Maximum detector number (inclusive)")
args = parser.parse_args()

det_min = args.det_min
det_max = args.det_max

# Load the data
# Assumes columns: evid det pvekin ioni
data = np.loadtxt("soho/eph-soho-photons-high-sensitive.hits")

# Extract columns
evid = data[:, 0]
det = data[:, 1]
```



```

pvekin = data[:, 2]
ioni = data[:, 3]

# Apply filters: all detectors in range, with valid pvekin and ioni
mask = (det >= det_min) & (det <= det_max) & (ioni > 0.01) & (pvekin > 0.01)
filtered_pvekin = pvekin[mask]
filtered_ioni = ioni[mask]
filtered_det = det[mask]

# Define log-spaced bins for histograms, multiplied by 1000 (e.g. converting MeV to keV)
x_bins = 1000 * np.logspace(np.log10(0.01), np.log10(filtered_pvekin.max()), 50)
y_bins = 1000 * np.logspace(np.log10(0.01), np.log10(filtered_ioni.max()), 50)

# Plot 2D histogram for all selected detectors
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
plt.hist2d(filtered_pvekin * 1000, filtered_ioni * 1000, bins=[x_bins, y_bins], norm=LogNorm())
plt.colorbar(label='Log counts')
plt.xscale('log')
plt.yscale('log')
plt.xlabel('pvekin [keV]')
plt.ylabel('ioni [keV]')
plt.title(f'2D Histogram of Ioni vs Pvekin (det {det_min}-{det_max})')
plt.grid(True, which='both', ls='--')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

# Prepare for 1D histograms
scale_factor = (100) / 1e9
bin_centers = np.sqrt(x_bins[:-1] * x_bins[1:])
total_counts = np.zeros_like(bin_centers)
bin_widths = np.diff(x_bins)

# Use distinct colors (cycling if more than 10)
num_dets = det_max - det_min + 1
cmap = plt.get_cmap('tab10')
colors = [cmap(i % cmap.N) for i in range(num_dets)]

# Plot 1D line histograms for each detector separately
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
for idx, d in enumerate(range(det_min, det_max + 1)):
    det_mask = (det == d) & (ioni > 0.01) & (pvekin > 0.01)
    det_pvekin = pvekin[det_mask]
    if len(det_pvekin) == 0:
        continue
    counts, _ = np.histogram(det_pvekin * 1000, bins=x_bins)
    scaled_counts = counts * scale_factor
    #scaled_counts /= bin_widths
    total_counts += scaled_counts
    plt.plot(bin_centers, scaled_counts, drawstyle='steps-mid', label=f'Det {d}', color=colors

```



```
# Plot the sum of all histograms
plt.plot(bin_centers, total_counts, drawstyle='steps-mid', color='black', linewidth=2.5, label

plt.xscale('log')
plt.yscale('log')
plt.xlabel('pvekin [keV]')
plt.ylabel('Scaled Counts')
plt.title(f'Scaled 1D Histogram of Pvekin by Detector ({det_min}-{det_max})')
plt.legend()
plt.grid(True, which='both', ls='--')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```


A5.2 Ion computation

A5.2.1 Geometry Description Markup Language (GDML) file to compute SSDF response to an isotropic electron, proton and helium distribution

```
# The following command assures that the run starts allways with the same seed
/random/setSeeds 5544293 7121843

# Choose the instrument model see deliverable D2.1
#/gdml/file /home/local1/G4VM/EPHIN/ephin.gdml
/gdml/file /home/local1/G4VM/EPHIN/ephin_soho_shield.gdml
#/gdml/file /home/local1/G4VM/EPHIN/ephin_chandra_shield.gdml

# set the cuts (see GEANT documentation)
/run/setCut 0.001 mm

# Number of CPUs to be used for the computation Change only if you know your hardware
/run/numberOfThreads 1

# Finalize the physics to be used
/run/initialize

# Output control (see GPS documentation)
/run/verbose 0
/event/verbose 0
/tracking/verbose 0
# We only write out the event id, the Volume that was hit,
# the energy with which the particle was generated
# and the energy loss in the corresponding volume.
/sd/verbose 1
/sd/format evid det pvekin ioni

/sd/file output/soho/eph-soho-helium-iso # for helium
/sd/file output/soho/eph-soho-protons-iso # for protons
/sd/file output/soho/eph-soho-electrons-iso # for electrons

/gps/particle ion
/gps/ion 2 4 0 0

#/gps/particle proton use for protons
#/gps/particle e- use for electrons

/gps/ene/type Pow
/gps/ene/alpha -1.
# for Helium
/gps/ene/min 40 MeV
/gps/ene/max 400 GeV

# for Protons
# /gps/ene/min 10 MeV
```



```
# /gps/ene/max 100 GeV

# for electrons
# /gps/ene/min 0.1 MeV
# /gps/ene/max 0.1 GeV
/gps/pos/type Surface
/gps/pos/shape Sphere
/gps/pos/centre 0 0 8.765 cm
/gps/pos/radius 25.0 cm # ensure that the isotropy is fullfilled within 10 %
/gps/ang/type cos

/run/beamOn 100000000
```